

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT, EXPERIENCE AND SATISFACTION ON ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

We hope to discover how employee engagement, employee satisfaction, and overall organisational performance are related to each other in this study. This study employed a descriptive research design. In order to test a hypothesis, a questionnaire and convenience sampling approach were used. Using SPSS 22, exploratory factor analysis was performed on a sample of 180 employees from various private banking organisations in Delhi-NCR. The study's findings based on regression analysis, show that improving the performance of Delhi-private NCR's banking firms has been mostly attributed to a rise in staff involvement, satisfaction, and experience. Effective use has been made of the concepts of employee involvement, experience, and satisfaction to raise company performance.

Keywords: Private banking, Regression, employee satisfaction, Employee engagement, employee experience,

I. INTRODUCTION

Effective utilisation of human resources is essential for gaining and retaining a competitive edge (Schaufeli & Salanova 2008) Competitive and experienced workers are critical to a company's success in the Private Banking market, which has grown rapidly and become more competitive over the past few years (Schwartz, 2015). Career progression leads to a natural progression toward recruiting more experienced workers, as evidenced by research studies (Dokko et. al,2009). Management must work on hiring and retaining the best and brightest employees because of the intricacy of the services. Businesses are placing a greater emphasis on the well-being of their employees than ever before. The (Durai & King, 2018). In order to achieve end goals, companies are realising that they must first treat their employees well. In attempt to provide a great work experience, the company must examine three areas: technology, physical space, and culture (Jacob Morgan, 2017). All human resource management strategies should be aimed at not only maintaining these personnel, but also getting them enthused and committed to the company's objective in the long run . The competitive nature of the global economy implies that organisations are placing more importance on employee engagement, employee experience, and employee satisfaction. An

investigation into how employee engagement, experience, and satisfaction affect organisational performance is the topic of this study. For the suggested study, researchers wanted to conduct accessibility research with respondents from a private banking organisation.

In the present study, the following aims are taken into account:

- To identify the factors affecting Organisational Performance
- To analyze the impact of selected variables on organisational performance.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for organisational Performance

A. Employee Engagement

Employee engagement techniques are the biggest challenge facing HR practitioners (Macey and Schneider 2008). Employee involvement is the subject of debate. Engaged employees are defined as those who are motivated by their work to achieve the goals of the organisation (Shuck and Wollard 2010). From an organisational standpoint, one can state that an engaged employee aims to increase business outcomes and productivity as well as the overall profitability of the organisation. Focus here is on elements that influence employee satisfaction and productivity. The term "engagement" refers to a person's basic psychological needs, such as their emotional and social needs while working in an organisation, as well as the materials necessary to work for a greater goal. When an employee is engaged in their work, they feel good about themselves. An employee's work environment and interpersonal interactions are developed as a routine operational activity in the creation of employee engagement. A disengaged employee is unable to fulfil their full potential, even if their talent is great. Managers play a crucial role in fostering a culture of employee engagement. According to one of the studies, managers are responsible for 71% of the variance in employee satisfaction.

Employee Experiences

All aspects of the employee experience, including attracting, retaining, and developing employees, go under this umbrella term. Accordingly, there has been little empirical research done to distinguish between what an organisation intends to achieve and what it actually does (Whitener, 2001). Everything from important life events and personal relationships to technology use in the workplace to the actual work environment that affects an employee's life cycle (appointment through retirement) is considered part of the employee experience. Leaders and managers should maintain a consistent tone in the workplace in order to improve the employee experience.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the sum total of a person's feelings about his or her work environment. It is a positive or negative reaction to the numerous aspects of one's work. It's a person's overall attitude and assessment of their work. As described by Baridam & Nwibere (2008), Job satisfaction is the state of being content or unsatisfied with one's job, with his or her work environment, colleagues, and the job itself. A person who is content with their employment has a good outlook on their work, whereas someone who is dissatisfied has a negative outlook on their work (Puskpakumari 2008). Worker satisfaction is a result of how well their work contributes to the things that matter most to them.

According to Cranny et al (1992), good employee morale is a result of job satisfaction. A disgruntled employee's unhappiness can trickle down to the rest of the company, either directly or by word-of-mouth. This can have a significant impact on morale and productivity throughout the entire workforce. Because of this, a disgruntled worker is a severe danger to the success of any company. Increased employee loyalty is a result of greater job satisfaction. It is more likely that an employee who is content with his or her job would stay with the company for the long term, whereas an employee who is dissatisfied will continually be looking for a new opportunity. The quality of the work and productivity of employees are both improved as a result of higher levels of job satisfaction and increased levels of employee motivation (Aaron et al., 2015).

Job happiness can also be a powerful recruiting tool. As a result, employees who are happy in their jobs as a whole are more likely to seek out those they know who possess the required talents and abilities to assist the business. As a result, when current employees speak well of the company, potential employees see it as a place they want to work. This helps to bring in the best and the brightest to their companies.

A more contented workforce is less likely to have high rates of employee turnover and lower levels of absenteeism. According to Bass (1965), employee happiness can have a major impact on a company's bottom line. This is due to the fact that reduced turnover means lower recruitment and lower training expenditures because of the lower turnover. According to Kasim and Ghaffar (2012), employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be more loyal, self-confident, and committed to the company, which in turn improves productivity and reduces absences and turnover (Linda & Michael, 2014). As a result, a company's commitment to its employees is strengthened when its people are happy in their jobs.

Employee Engagement and Organisational Performance

According to a number of academics, employee involvement has a direct impact on organisational success. More and more motivated workers are, the better the organisation performs. Devi (2017) evaluated this relationship between employee engagement and organisational performance as beneficial. This is also the position of Devi (2017), who argues, however, that organisations can use employee engagement as a strategic tool to improve numerous business processes. Excellent workplace environment, as per Wellins and Bernthal (2015), stimulate individuals to be motivated and perform brilliantly in order to increase production and profitability, offer greater products or services, and better utilise organisational resources. According to Kazimoto (2016), in order to encourage employees, managers should place a greater emphasis on financial issues.

H1: Employee Engagement has a significant impact on organisational performance

Employee experience and Organisational Performance

There are a number of different organisations that a person has worked for, and each of these organisations contributes to the complete experience of the employee (Dokko et.al. 2009). Employees' employment outcomes and company performance increase as a result of their work experience, which includes both occupational and industry-specific behaviours. There is a correlation between the amount of time an employee spends in an industry or occupation and the quantity of human capital they have, as stated in Rauch and Frese's 2000 Human Capital hypothesis (Rauch and Frese 2000). The authors (Hsiung & Wang, 2012). Tesco for example feels that employing experienced workers will allow them to be more innovative, so boosting both their own and the company's overall performance (Al-Dujaili, 2012). According to a survey conducted by WorkTrend (2016) on behalf of IBM, employees who have previous work experience are more likely to have a feeling of accomplishment and dynamism, which in turn leads to higher levels of performance and contribution.

H2: Employee Experience has a significant impact on organisational performance

Employee Satisfaction and Organizational Performance

Job satisfaction and performance have been extensively studied in a variety of ororganizational contexts. ReThe results these inquiries have not converged on a single path. Cummings (1970) outlined three distinct viewpoints on this relationship.. Both performance and contentment are directly linked to a person's level of happiness. Kornhanuser and Sharp (1976) have done more than 30 studies to determine how satisfaction and performance are linked. Worker satisfaction does not correlate with turnover or production quality, according to Katzell, Barnet, and Porker (1952). Employer performance is positively correlated with job satisfaction, according to Smith and Cranny (1968). Lee and Chan (1996) found that job satisfaction and productivity are linked, and that the more satisfied an employee is, the more likely they are to try to improve productivity. According to Carroll, Keflas and Watson (1964), contentment and job production are interdependent. Due to the apparent expectation of awards or other positive results, they suggest that performance encourages additional work effort. Effort drives forceful presentation, which leads to fulfilment in an urgent relationship.

Remuneration frameworks have a significant impact on the relationship between satisfaction and performance, according to David, Joseph, and William (1970).

This is the consequence of the last point. For Baridam and Nwibere (2008), the importance of this concept is not because it solves the contradiction of happiness and performance, but because it has a proactive research and managerial consequences.

H3: Employee Satisfaction has a significant impact on organisational performance

METHODOLOGY

This study relies on both primary and secondary sources of information. The primary data was gathered through the use of a well-structured questionnaire. A sample of 180 employees from various private banking organisations in the Delhi NCR region was chosen because it was not possible to contact all of the employees in the business due to time and resources.

A five-point Likert scale was used to collect data on all of the measures. It was provided to the employees in person and by mail, along with a brief description of the study's goals, with a copy of the final questionnaire. The final data collection, which included responses from 180 employees, was used for further study. With the study's goals in mind, statistical techniques like correlation and regression analysis were used to extract useful insights from the data set.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

		Frequency	Valid %
Gender Profile	Male	157	87.2
	Female	23	12.8
Age Profile	21-29 years	25	13.9
	30-39 years	56	31.1
	40-49 years	34	18.9
	46-55 years	43	23.9
	60 Years and older	22	12.2
Highest Education Level	Diploma/ 10+2	23	12.8
	Bachelor Degree	50	27.8
	Master Degree	75	41.7
	Professional Education	32	17.8
Length of Affiliation	1-2 years	40	22.2
	3-5 years	63	35.0
	6-10 years	65	36.1
	11 years and more	12	6.7
Current Designation	managers	47	26.1
	Executive	62	34.4
	Supervisors	60	33.3
	Others	11	6.1
Marital Status	Married	160	88.9
	Un-Married	20	11.1

Reliability Analysis

For all measures utilised in this study, cronbach alpha values greater than 0.70 confirm their reliability and internal consistency.

Table 2: Results of the Reliability Examination

	Independent Variable	Cronbach Alpha
1	Employee Engagement	.822
2	Employee Experience	.832
3	Employee Satisfaction	.819
4	Organisational Performance	.769
Over all Reliability of the Questionnaire		.838

Cronbach's alpha values in Table 2 are higher than the permissible cutoff value of 0.7. An alpha value of 0.838 from Cronbach's alpha tests the questionnaire's overall dependability.

Correlation Analysis

This shows that there is a substantial correlation between the independent variables. Each of the four factors evaluated had a strong association with the overall variable. 'Organisational Performance' is strongly linked to all three independent variables, as well as to each other. Organizational Performance (0.844) has the strongest correlation with "employee experience," followed by "Employee Engagement" and "Employee Satisfaction" (0.736).

Table 3: Pearson Correlations

	Employee Engagement	Employee Experience	Employee Satisfaction	Organisational Performance
Employee Engagement	1			
Employee Experience	.806**	1		
Employee Satisfaction	.736**	.777**	1	
Organisational Performance	.804**	.844**	.823**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

REGRESSION ANALYSIS: HYPOTHESIS TESTING

In order to represent the link between two independent variables and one dependent variable, regression analysis is used. Organizational Performance is used as a dependent variable in a number of different regression models, all of which are being evaluated. Organizational Performance is used as the dependent variable in regression models that take three distinct characteristics into account: Employee Experience; Employee Satisfaction; and Employee Engagement (Figure 1).

It was revealed that three variables (Employee Experience, Employee Satisfaction, and Employee Engagement) were significant predictors of "Organisational Performance" based on the findings of the step-wise regression analysis in Tables 4a and 4b. According to the R square of 0.801, these three factors may explain "Organisational Performance" in Table 4 to a degree of 80.1 percent (a). For the regression model, the "ANOVA results are reported, confirming validity at the 95% confidence level," as shown in Table 4(b). Employee Experience, Satisfaction, and Engagement Factors' beta values in Table 4(c) show that they have an impact on "Organisational Performance," and these results are pretty indicative of their importance on that end.

Table 4 (a): Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.844 ^a	.713	.711	.370
2	.885 ^b	.783	.781	.322
3	.895 ^c	.801	.798	.309

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Experience

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Experience , Employee Satisfaction

c. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Experience , Employee Satisfaction , Employee Engagement

Table 4(b): ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	60.361	1	60.361	441.619	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.329	178	.137		
	Total	84.691	179			
2	Regression	66.329	2	33.164	319.691	.000 ^c
	Residual	18.362	177	.104		
	Total	84.691	179			
3	Regression	67.877	3	22.626	236.837	.000 ^d
	Residual	16.814	176	.096		
	Total	84.691	179			

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Experience

c. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Experience , Employee Satisfaction

d. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Experience , Employee Satisfaction , Employee Engagement

Table 4(c):Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.513	.108		4.747	.000
	Employee Experience	.791	.038	.844	21.015	.000
2	(Constant)	.398	.095		4.174	.000
	Employee Experience	.485	.052	.517	9.308	.000
3	Employee Satisfaction	.348	.046	.421	7.584	.000
	(Constant)	.376	.092		4.106	.000
	Employee Experience	.352	.060	.376	5.888	.000
	Employee Satisfaction	.293	.046	.355	6.358	.000
	Employee Engagement	.198	.049	.239	4.026	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Organisational Performance

TEST RESULTS FOR HYPOTHESES

There were three hypotheses put forward in the study's conceptual framework, and Table 5 demonstrates that all of them have been accepted.

Table 5: Summary of Test Results for Hypotheses

Hy . No .	Independent Variables	to	Dependent Variables	R-Square	Beta Coefficient	t-value	Sig Value	Status of Hypotheses
H1	Employee Experience	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)	0.801	.376	5.888	0.000	Accepted
H2	Employee Satisfaction	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)		.355	6.358	0.000	Accepted
H3	Employee Engagement	→	Organisational Performance (ORGP)		.239	4.026	0.000	Accepted

CONCLUSION

The basic aim of this research was to better understand how the employee experience, employee satisfaction, and employee engagement impact organisational performance. Three independent factors were used to assess the overall performance of the organisation. Employee Experience, Employee Satisfaction, and Employee Engagement were all found to be significant predictors of "Organisational Performance," according to the findings. Thus, data from this study suggest that employee experience, satisfaction, and engagement are favourably connected with organisational performance. An engaged employee's experience of job satisfaction has a significant impact on business productivity and profit, from a management perspective. As a result, it is imperative to investigate the most significant aspects influencing employees' engagement, experience, and happiness in order to improve the organization's overall performance.

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